

SiC/SiC COMPOSITES FABRICATED BY ELECTROPHORETIC DEPOSITION COMBINED WITH POLYMER INFILTRATION AND PYROLYSIS PROCESS

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ABSTRACT

Continuous silicon carbide (SiC) fiber reinforced SiC matrix (SiC/SiC) composites are considered to be the promising candidate materials in aerospace and nuclear fields, because of its outstanding properties such as low density, high specific strength, high specific modulus, high temperature resistance, high thermal shock resistance, low radioactivity and high radiation resistance. The thermal conductivity of existing SiC/SiC composites are low, especially for the SiC/SiC composites fabricated by Polymer Infiltration and Pyrolysis (PIP) process. In this paper, in order to improve the thermal conductivity of PIP-SiC/SiC composites, the SiC micro-powder was introduced into SiC matrix by using Electrophoretic Deposition (EPD) process, which can increase the crystallinity, density and purity of PIP-SiC/SiC composites.

Before the preparation of SiC/SiC composites using EPD combined with PIP process, the SiC matrix containing SiC micro-Powder fabricated by Cold Press combined with PIP Process. The weight ratios of SiC micro-powder are 10%, 30%, 50% and 70% respectively, and the cold pressing pressure is 20 MPa. The results show that with the increase of SiC micro-powder content, the sample density increases, the porosity decreases greatly, and the thermal conductivity improves remarkably. The thermal conductivity of the samples prepared by doping 70% SiC micro-powder is 2.38 W/(m·K), nearly four times that of the samples prepared by doping 10% SiC micro-powder.

It can be concluded that doping SiC micro-powder into SiC matrix obtained by PIP process can significantly improve the thermal conductivity of SiC matrix. Therefore, the EPD process is used to introduce SiC micro-powder into SiC fiber fabric, and then PIP process is carried out in order to improve the thermal conductivity of SiC/SiC composites. The results show that the properties of the SiC/SiC composites prepared by EPD combined with PIP process decreased greatly, compared with the composites without SiC powder in the matrix. The density of SiC/SiC composites prepared by EPD combined with PIP process is less than that of composites without SiC powder, and the thermal conductivity of the composites has not achieved the desired results. According to the previous research results of our group, SiC fibers are vulnerable to current damage during electrophoretic deposition, resulting in a decrease in the performance of SiC fibers. The reasons need further analysis in the follow-up work.

Properties of SiC matrix

Table1 Density and porosity of SiC matrix doped with different content of beta-SiC powder

Ratio (wt%)	Density(g/cm ³)	Open porosity (%)
10	1.96	7.77
30	2.03	4.42
50	2.21	2.89
70	2.24	2.20

Table 2 Thermal Conductivity of SiC matrix doped with different content of beta-SiC powder

Ratio (wt%)	Thermal conductivity (W/(m·K))	Thermal diffusion coefficient (mm ² /s)	Specific heat capacity (J/(g·K))
10	0.65	0.736	0.452
30	1.31	1.106	0.582
50	2.04	1.806	0.587
70	2.38	2.288	0.406

Properties of SiC/SiC composites

Table 3 Properties of SiC/SiC composites fabricated by EPD combined with PIP process

Sample	Density (g/cm ³)	Open porosity (%)	Flexural Strength (MPa)	Elastic modulus (GPa)	Fracture toughness (MPa·m ^{1/2})	Thermal Conductivity (W/(m·K))
Tradition	2.33	7.7	425±41.7	131±11.1	13.6±1.6	3.22
EPD	2.22	8.3	288±33.7	84.8±10.1	8±1.1	2.3

Microstructure of SiC/SiC composites

Fig.1 Stress-displacement curves of SiC/SiC composites fabricated by EPD combined with PIP process

Fig.2 Fracture micrographs of SiC/SiC composites fabricated by EPD combined with PIP process